

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Data Management Plan
Deliverable D7.2**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D7.2

About this document

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<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable is the first version of the Data Management Plan of the project. It sets up the context of how the data will be managed during the four years. It includes the numerical data but most importantly in this project, the management of the software and the personal data. It will be revised at Month 24 (D7.2 - Update of data management plan) and Month 47 (D7.4 - Final update of data management plan).

2. Conclusion & Results

The main conclusions of this deliverable are that the data produced within the project, even if not kept, will be obtained with version-controlled software ensuring the reproducibility and FAIRness of the data and that the personal data gathered will be done following the GDPR rules.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable has a special status compared with the rest of the deliverables and milestones of the project, as it reports on the data management and not the actual scientific or technical results of the project. Therefore, it doesn't contribute directly or indirectly to the macro-objectives or specific goals of the project, but rather describes the compliance with the generic rules of data management.

4. Project data and software

4.1 Data Summary

As mentioned in the summary, none of the work packages are planned to generate scientific numerical data as most of the work of the project will consist of software developments and recommendations on infrastructure. The outputs of the numerical models of work packages 1 (“Support to effective applications”) and 2 (“Develop community tools”) as well as the data of work package 3 (“Tackling the data challenge”) are only temporary data (mostly in GRIB¹ and NetCDF² format) that will be stored by the individual partners on their own premises.

Work packages 5 (“Training and capacity building”), 6 (“Community engagement, dissemination and exploitation”) and 7 (“Project management”) will gather some personal data: names, institutions and email addresses of the project partners, assistants to workshops etc... This data will be kept in the coordinator's premises, following the GDPR requirements, only during the duration of the project.

The software generated during the project will be documented and version controlled in the BSC gitlab which is hosted in a dedicated virtual machine, with regular backups.

¹ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/What+are+GRIB+files+and+how+can+I+read+them>

² <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

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The two other “platforms” with information of the project are the project wiki (hosted at BSC in a backed up virtual machine) and the project website (hosted at DKRZ).

4.2 FAIR data

Considering the absence of numerical data, the data FAIRness³ (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) in the context of the project has been considered but is not applicable here.

4.3 Other research outputs

The project is targeting the publication of peer reviewed papers in open journals, ensuring the dissemination of the results of the research conducted.

4.4 Allocation of resources

The data management of the project is handled in work package 7, with the current deliverable and its two following revisions. One person from BSC will be dedicated to this work, with 2 PMs from the 33 of this work package.

4.5 Data security

The data security concerns here only the backup of the virtual machines hosting the gitlab, project wiki and website described in section 4.1.

4.6 Ethics

The techniques developed in this project will only utilise geophysical data/parameters obtained from numerical weather and climate model simulations. No personal or environmental data of any kind will be used. Therefore, we identify no ethical issues of any kind related to human rights and values when applying techniques related to artificial intelligence or machine learning in the framework of this project.

5. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

5.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

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X	The general public (PU).
X	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Not applicable.

5.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

Not applicable.

5.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.